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Kuki traditional institutions and development: Role of village chiefs in Manipur

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'Housa' (Chieftainship) is the oldest form of tribal administration that still works among the Kuki tribes of Manipur. Though in many tribal areas of Northeast it was abolished and replaced by Village Council, Chieftainship still functions as the system of local self government in the Kuki villages of Manipur. The present study attempts to assess the role of Kuki institution of chieftainship in development from the perspective of the chiefs themselves. The present study probes into the role perceived and played by the chiefs. As a prelude, it tries to present the demographic, social and economic structural bases of the chiefs. In addition, the present study tries to identify the major institutional constraints to chieftainship in achieving development. The study is cross sectional in nature and exploratory in design and based on the primary data collected through structured questionnaire. The chiefs of villages in the most developed and least developed blocks in the Kuki areas of Manipur constitute the respondents of the study. The results of study indicate the resilience of the traditional Kuki institution of 'Housa'. The village chiefs perceived both the traditional and developmental roles both in the most and least developed blocks invariably. The chiefs' socio economic structural bases as well as their exposure to development functionaries have not influenced their role perceptions. To deal with them effectively they suggest strengthening and empowering chief system, allocation of more funds for development of Kuki areas, special financial assistance for the chief and inclusion of chiefs in the district and state administration. However, it is argued that this system needs to be replaced with more democratic and responsible local governance system similar to that of the panchayati raj institutions functioning in the rural India.

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Introduction

'Housa' (Chieftainship) is the oldest form of tribal administration known to have stood the test of time which still functions among the Kuki tribes of Manipur.

Though in many tribal areas of North East Chieftainship was abolished and replaced by the Village Council System, chieftainship still remains the only mode of village administration among the Kukis of Manipur.

Recently, some scholars have argued that the hereditary chief system is neither authoritative nor despotic. A deeper study of the history of these tribes shows a very clear role of the chiefs in ensuring the development of the poor, the weak and vulnerable sections of the village communities. However, the traditional institution of chieftainship deteriorated after the British occupation of the tribal areas. In the post independence period, it did not show any signs of improvement due to various social, economic and political structural factors.

As regards the literature, the role of chieftainship in governing the tribal communities is a recurrent feature of tribal studies in the Northeast India. The Kuki chieftainship system has been described in a number of works (Gangte, 2003; Shaw, 1929; Soppitt, 1893). The chieftainship and its role among the Naga tribes, (Majumdar & Madan 1980; Chib 1984), tribes of Tripura (Sengupta, 1994; Baveja, 1982), Meghalaya (Das & Basu, 2005; Momin & Mawlong 2004; Roy & Majumdar, 1981), and Mizoram (Sangkima, 2004; Parry, 1922; Thangchungnunga, 1997) had been described.

Though these studies provide useful information, there are a few research gaps could be noted. Firstly, the demographic, socio economic or political profile of the chieftains is hardly described in any study. Secondly, the role of the chiefs perceived by the chiefs themselves has not been assessed. Thirdly, the achievements and contributions of the chiefs to the development of the tribal people are hardly probed into. Fourthly, the constraints in the functioning of the chieftainship are hardly explored into. The present study attempts to fill these gaps in the study.

The present paper is presented in three sections. The first section outlines the research problem and methodology. In the second section, the results and discussion are presented while in the last section the concluding observations are presented.

The Problem and Methodology

In this section, the research problem and the methodological aspects of the present study are presented.

The Problem

The purpose of the present study is to understand the role perceived and played by the chiefs. In addition to these, the study tries to understand the major institutional constraints linked with chieftainship in achieving tribal development. This study also presents the demographic, social, economic, political structural bases of the chieftains. In the light of the findings, a few measures for policymaking and social work intervention are also suggested. The results of this study on these aspects will be useful for policy makers and social workers to enhance the quality of tribal life in the Northeast region.

Methodology

The present study is cross sectional in nature and exploratory in design. It is based on the primary data collected through structured questionnaire from the chiefs of villages in the Kuki areas of Manipur. The survey was conducted during December 2006 to February 2007.

By using stratified random sampling, data were collected where different blocks in two tribal districts viz., Churachandpur and Tamenglong of Manipur were classified into most developed and least developed. In these blocks, one most developed block and one least developed block were selected at random. All the village chiefs in the 4 selected blocks were distributed a structured questionnaire. 103 Questionnaires were distributed to the chieftains, of which only 37 filled in questionnaires were returned after 2 visits by the investigator. SPSS package was used to process and analyse the data. Cross tabulation, averages, percentages and proportions were used in analysis of data. Apart from these Karl Pearson's product moment correlation coefficients have been used for analysis.

Results and Discussion

The present section is devoted to present the results of statistical analysis of the primary data collected. This section has been presented with two sub sections viz., profile of chiefs, and institution of chieftainship at work.

Social Structural Bases of Chiefs

The profile of the chiefs presented in the present section covers the demographic, social, economic and political structural bases of the chiefs surveyed.

1. Demographic Bases

The demographic bases of the chief include the structural characteristics such as gender, age group, marital status, education status, type and size of family (see table 1).

As regards gender most of the chiefs are male and the women had the least chances to hold the position of Chieftainship because the traditional institution of Chief is patrilineal and also patriarchal. Out of the total 37 respondents, only 1 of the chiefs are female. This shows the low representation of women in community power structure in most tribal areas.

As regards age most of the chiefs are middle aged (35-60 years). More than three fourth of the chiefs in most developed blocks(67%) and more than one half of them in least developed blocks(58%) are of middle age. The mean years of age worked out also indicates similar picture of age. The average age of a chief in both the blocks respectively was worked out to 57 years. All the chiefs were married. Interestingly, there are no unmarried chief.

As regards education most of the chief had high school education in both the most and least developed blocks. More than one half of the chiefs in the least

developed blocks (58%) and more than three fourth of them in the most developed blocks (78%) had high school education. Interestingly, a notable proportion of the chiefs in both the types of blocks had education above higher secondary school. Over one fourth of the chiefs in least developed blocks (26%) and one tenth of them in the most developed blocks (11%) had education above the higher secondary level. The mean years of education of the chiefs in the most developed blocks was worked out at 10 years while that of the least developed blocks is worked out to be 9 years.

As regards type of family, joint family is found to be predominant type among the chiefs in both types of blocks. More than four fifth of the chiefs in least developed blocks(84 %) and most of the chiefs in most developed block(94%) reportedly lived in joint families.

Though the family size of the chiefs is predominantly large in both the types of blocks it is more prominent in most developed blocks. A little more than 83 percent of the chiefs in the most developed blocks and 68 percent of the chiefs in the least developed blocks had large families. The mean size of family is worked out at a tag more than 8 for least developed blocks while the same is close to 9 in most developed blocks.

2. Social Structural Bases

Social Structural bases of Chiefs discussed as under are tribe, religion and denomination. These characteristics are observed and discussed as under (see table 2).

The chiefs belong to five different Kuki tribes residing in the study area. They are Thadou, Vaiphei, Gangte, Zou and Aimol. Chiefs belonging to Thadou tribe are majority in both the types of blocks while a significant proportion of them belong to Gangte and Vaiphei tribes. This representation reflects the population composition of the Kuki tribes in the study area. More than one half of the chiefs in least developed blocks(63%) and half of them in most developed blocks(50%) belong to the Thadou tribe. Vaiphei and Gangte are the other tribes which have significant representation among the chiefs. Chiefs belonging to Vaiphei constitute one third of the chiefs in the most developed blocks (33%) while Gangte constitutes over one fourth of the chiefs in the least developed blocks (26%).

There are two religions practiced among the chiefs in the surveyed area. They are Christianity and Judaism. All of the chiefs of the least developed blocks belonged to Christianity while over one tenth of the chiefs in most developed blocks practice Judaism. The presence of Judaism can be attributed to the belief among the Kukis of Manipur and Mizos of Mizoram that they are one of the lost tribes of Israel. Kukis initially embraced Christianity and some of them had further converted to Judaism believing that they were one of the lost tribes of Jews.

The different denominations found in the present study area were Evangelical Churches Association, Baptist, Presbyterian, Roman Catholic, Pentecostal, Messianic, Judaism and local denominations. Evangelical church is found to be predominant among the chiefs in most developed blocks (39%) while Baptist church is found to be highest among the least developed blocks (47%). Nearly one

fifth of the chiefs in most developed block belonged to Presbyterian denomination (17%).

3. Economic Structural Bases

The economic structural bases of the chiefs are discussed in terms of the main occupation, subsidiary occupation and their level of household income (see table 3).

The chiefs subsist on cultivation, government employment, government pension, petty businessmen or public service. The chiefs were by and large cultivators in both the types of blocks. The occupational structure of the chiefs in most developed blocks was more diversified than that of the least developed blocks. Over four fifth the chiefs in least developed blocks (84%) and more than one half of them in the most developed blocks (61%) were cultivators. Interestingly, over one tenth of the chiefs (16 %) in both the blocks were in various government services.

As regards subsidiary occupation for over one third of the chiefs there was no such occupation. More than one third of the chiefs in least developed blocks (42%) and in the most developed blocks (39%) had no subsidiary occupation at all. But agriculture and horticulture are the significant subsidiary occupations among the chiefs in both the blocks. One fourth of the chiefs in least developed blocks (26%) and more than one fourth in the most developed blocks (39%) had agriculture as subsidiary occupation.

The annual household income of the chiefs was classified into four levels viz., Below Rs 30000, Rs 30000 to 60000, Rs 60000 – 100000, Above Rs 100000. Most of the chiefs in both the blocks had annual income between Rs. 30,000 – Rs. 60,000 in the most developed (56%) as well as least developed blocks (42%). The mean annual income of the chiefs indicates that the chiefs in the most developed blocks had better living conditions over their counterparts in the least developed blocks (see table 3). It seems from the above observations that the chiefs in spite of controlling large area of land were not very rich though they cannot be exactly labelled as poor either.

4. Political Affiliation of the Chiefs

The chiefs are usually active in politics, as they are typically the most influential persons in their respective villages. They are found to usually affiliate to some political parties and even hold important positions in them. The political affiliations of the chiefs and parties they are affiliated are described as under (see table 4).

Majority of the chiefs in both types of blocks are supporters of one political party or the other rather than being members. More than one half of the chiefs in the least developed blocks(53%) and half of the chiefs in most developed blocks(50%) were reportedly the supporters of a particular political party.

The political parties found to have supporters among the chiefs in the study area include Indian National Congress (INC), Communist Party of India (CPI), Lok Jansakthi Party (LJP), Samajwadi Party (SP), Nationalist Congress Party

(NCP), and Rashtriya Janada Dal (RJD) though half of the chiefs kept them aloof from politics. Interestingly, all these are national political parties operating in various states of India. Most of the chiefs reportedly are supporters of Indian National Congress (INC), which is at the time of the survey the ruling party at both state and central levels. INC is reportedly supported by nearly one third of the chiefs in the least developed blocks (32%), and one third of chiefs in the most developed blocks (33%). Strikingly, the Nationalist Congress Party (NCP), Rashtriya Janada Dal (RJD) and Lok Jansakthi Party (LJP) are supported by a few of the chiefs in both the blocks.

Institution of Chieftainship at Work

The previous sub section described the structural bases of the chief. With that backdrop the profile of chieftainship, pattern of consultation in decision-making, exposure to development functionaries, chiefs' role perception, achievements and correlates of role perception and achievement in this section.

1. Profile of Chieftainship

The profile of the Chieftainship is discussed in terms of the duration of chieftainship, number of generation as chief, mode of acquisition of chieftainship and generations expected (see table 5).

The duration of Chieftainship or years of acting as chief is categorized into three groups viz., less than 15 years, 15-35 years and 35 years above. The greatest proportion of chiefs had 15 to 35 years duration of chieftainship in both least developed (42%) and most developed blocks (39%). Nearly one third of the chiefs in the least developed blocks and most developed blocks had more than 15 years duration of service while more than one fourth of the chiefs in both the types of blocks had less than 15 years in office as chief. The mean duration of chieftainship in the least developed blocks is computed to be 27 years and the same is 28 years for the chiefs in the most developed blocks.

As regards the number of generations acting as chiefs, the results indicate that mostly the chieftainship has been occupied for about two generations in both the types of blocks. One half of the chiefs in the most developed blocks and nearly one third of the chiefs in the least developed blocks reportedly had acted as chiefs for two generations. Nearly one third of the chiefs in the least developed blocks and more than one fifth of them in the most developed blocks reported had only one generation of chieftainship. The mean number of generation acting as chieftainship is computed at 2 in the least developed blocks and 2 in the most developed blocks.

Modes of acquisition of chieftainship observed in the study area include elders' choice, King/British appointment and purchase. Among these, the elders' choice and purchase are the prominent modes of acquisition in both the types of blocks. The elders reportedly chose 42 percent of the chiefs in least developed and 33 percent of them in developed blocks. One third of the chieftainships in most developed blocks (33%) while in least developed blocks (32%) are reportedly

acquired by purchase. King's appointment is also a significant mode in both the types of blocks. More than one fifth of the chieftainships are acquired by the chiefs' families by King's /British appointment in both the blocks.

As regards the number of generations, most of the chiefs in both the blocks are expected to be in office so long as the customary laws and practices continue to be relevant or as long as their lineage continues. More than one third of the chiefs in both the types of blocks expected the office would continue with their heirs so long as their lineage exists. Interestingly, over one tenth of the chiefs in both the types of blocks reported to continue in office of chief so long as the customary law exists (see table 5).

2. Pattern of Consultation in Decision Making

Decision-making is one of the important aspects of the governance at any level. In decision making, traditionally chiefs used to consult the elders in the past. Here in this section, an attempt has been made to assess the frequency of consultation by the chiefs in decision making with various groups in their villages. Consultation in decision making was in fact measured in terms frequency of chiefs' consultation with village elders, youth leaders, church leaders, own family members, knowledgeable persons, relatives, friends and school teachers. The frequency of consultation with each of the categories is measure with a four-point scale always (4), sometimes (3), rarely (2) and never (1). The mean consultation scores of each of these are presented in table 6.

There are significant differences between the most and least developed blocks in terms of the pattern of chiefs' consultation in decision-making. Interestingly, the chiefs of the villages in the most developed blocks had greater frequency of consultation in most of the categories in decision making as compared to their counterparts in the least developed blocks.

Majority of the chiefs reported to have 'always' consulted Village Elders (3.9), Youth Leaders (3.6), and Church Leaders (3.7) in the case of most developed blocks while in case of least developed blocks they 'always' consulted youth leaders (3.6) only while making decisions. The chiefs in most developed blocks 'sometimes' consulted their own Family Members (3.39), Knowledgeable Persons (3.39), Relatives (3.17), Friends (3.00), and School Teachers (2.89) in decision-making. On the other hand, the chiefs in least developed blocks 'sometimes' consulted village elders (3.4), Church Leaders (3.21), Own Family Members (3.47), Knowledgeable Persons (3.37), and Relatives (3.05) and they 'rarely' consulted friends (2.47) and school teachers (2.16).

3. Exposure to Developmental Functionaries

Development by and large is determined by the degree of exposure of the village leaders with the official and non-official development functionaries. The present sub section assesses the links between various development functionaries with the chiefs. The development functionaries include Member of Parliament (MP), Member of State Assembly (MLA), State Ministers, Deputy Commissioner (DC),

District Deputy Collector (DDC), Block Development Officer (BDO), Extension Officer (EO), Police Officer, Bank Manager, School Headmaster, Health Worker, and Agriculture Worker. The exposure of the chiefs has been measured in terms of 'yes' or 'no' type of close ended questions. The results are presented in table 7.

There is marginal difference between the chiefs of the two types of blocks. The mean index of exposure to development functionaries for the chiefs of least developed blocks is worked out at 0.67 while that of those of most developed blocks is 0.63.

Interestingly, a majority of the chiefs in both the types of blocks had exposure to MLA, BDO, DDC, Extension Officer (EO), Village Agriculture Worker (VAW), Deputy Commissioner (DC), Primary School Headmaster, Village Health Workers (Nurse) and any police officer. On the other hand Bank Managers, State Ministers, and Member of Parliament (MP) are known to only some of the chiefs.

4. Chiefs Role Perception: Traditional and Developmental

The performance of the chief in tribal development is expected to be influenced by the role perception of the chief. Role perception of chiefs has been conceptualised into two components viz., traditional role and developmental role. Traditional role perception of the chief is assessed in terms of the chiefs' traditional functions such as monitoring and deciding the dates for forest clearance, distribution of land, deciding land site for cultivation, protecting the village, ensuring order and justice, promoting hard work, integration, religiosity and spirituality, and honesty while promoting self-help, promotion of education, improving living condition, and preventing spread of disease are the functions considered for assessment of developmental role perception of the chief. These are measured in terms of a four-point scale with Strongly Agree (4) Agree (3) Disagree (2) Strongly Disagree (1). The simple average of all the functions in each of the dimension is considered as role perception score (see table 8).

As compared to traditional role, the developmental role is perceived more by the chiefs in both the types of blocks. The chiefs strongly agree with the developmental role of their institution in both the most developed blocks (3.7) and least developed blocks (3.8) while agreeing with their traditional roles as well. The traditional role perception score of the chiefs in least developed blocks is worked out to 3.5 and that of most developed block is 3.2. Indeed, the traditional institution of chieftainship seems to be resilient and do accommodate the modern challenges of improving the quality of life, education, health care etc.

5. Chiefs Achievements: Traditional and Developmental

Achievements of the Chiefs had been conceptualised into two dimensions - traditional and developmental. Developmental achievement is assessed in terms of social and physical infrastructure development and economic development. Settlement of disputes and justice, implementation of customary law and administrative development are considered as indicators of traditional achievement. Each of these indicators is measured by binary (yes 1 no =0)

variables. Simple average of all the indicators in each dimension is considered as indices of them (see table 9).

The chiefs by and large report developmental achievement to a greater extent as compared to their traditional achievement invariably in both the types of blocks. On an average 68 percent of the chiefs in least developed blocks and 69 percent of them in the most developed blocks report developmental achievement. On the other hand 26 percent of the chiefs in the former and 31 percent of them in the latter report traditional achievement.

The achievements of the chiefs in both the types of blocks is found to be highest in physical infrastructure development, which account for 74 per cent in least developed blocks and 84 percent in most developed blocks. Implementation of customary law as an achievement is found to be the lowest in the block in least developed block (5%) and in most developed block (11%). Economic development was found to be higher in least developed block (63%) than in most developed block (44%). Settlement of dispute and promotion of justice too is higher in least developed block (58%) than in most developed block (56%) while social infrastructure development is found to be higher in most developed block (78%) than in least developed block (68%). In the same way administrative development too is found to be higher in most developed block (28%) than in least developed block (16%). This shows that the common achievement of the Kuki chiefs in Manipur is in the field of physical and social infrastructure. Moreover, it can be inferred from the study that implementation of customary law is diminishing and the concern for it is very less (see table 9).

6. Correlates of Role Perception and Achievements of Chief

To identify the factors related to the role perception and achievements of the surveyed chiefs, a correlation analysis was conducted between background variables viz., types of blocks, age group, education status, level of income, duration of chieftainship, number of generation as chief, and exposure to development functionaries, traditional functions, developmental functions, traditional achievement, and developmental achievements. Karl Pearson's coefficients are also computed among the variables of exposure to development functionaries, traditional functions, developmental functions, traditional achievements, and developmental achievements (see table 10).

Exposure to development functionaries has no significant relationship with the types of blocks (-0.09), age group (-0.23), education status (0.05), level of income (-0.03), duration of chieftainship (0.02), and number of generation as chief (0.06).

Similarly, traditional role perception of the chiefs was not significantly related to type of blocks (-0.30), age group (-0.14), education status (0.16), level of income (-0.23), duration of chieftainship (0.05), number of generation as chief (0.12), and exposure to development functionaries (0.23).

Interestingly, developmental role perception had significant and positive relationship with traditional role perception (0.66). But it has no significant relationship with type of blocks (-0.14), age group (-0.11), education status (0.14), level of income (-0.15), duration of chieftainship (0.04), number of generation as

chief (-0.05), and exposure to development functionaries (0.03).

Traditional achievement of the chiefs had significant and positive relationship with age group (0.38). It seems as the age increases the perceived traditional achievement score of the chiefs also increases. But variables such as types of blocks (0.12), education status (0.10), level of income (0.28), duration of chieftainship (0.24), number of generation as chief (-0.02) had no significant association with traditional achievement of the chiefs. Strikingly, traditional achievements of the chiefs had no significant association with exposure to development functionaries (0.13), traditional role perception (-0.05) or developmental role perception (-0.21).

Developmental achievements of the chiefs is not significantly related to any of the variables viz., types of blocks (0.00), age group (-0.09), education status (-0.07), level of income (-0.05), duration of chieftainship (-0.04), number of generation as chiefs (0.04), exposure to development functionaries (0.31), traditional role (0.15), developmental role (-0.09), and traditional achievements (0.11)

Institutional Constraints and Suggestions

In this last section, the constraints perceived to affect the working of the chiefs in development and suggestions for their improvement are presented in two subsections.

1. Constraints to Effective Functioning of Chiefs

Constraints are those factors that obstruct the effective and smooth functioning of the chiefs in achieving the goals of development. The constraints according to the chiefs are related to factors like dealing with insurgent groups, poverty and illiteracy, lack of unity among villagers, and lack of infrastructure development. The study shows that insurgent organisations operating in Manipur as perceived as the major constraint to the effective functioning of the chiefs in most developed (56%) and in the least developed blocks (58%).

Poverty and illiteracy accounted for 53 percent in least developed block and 44 percent in most developed block. Lack of unity is another factor that vexes the chief in effective functioning, where it accounts for 47 percent and 39 percent in least developed block and most developed block respectively. Lack of infrastructure development seems to be arrived at as the least constraint to the effective functioning of chiefs (see table 11).

2. Suggestions for Effective Functioning of Chiefs

The chiefs were asked to suggest measures for their effective functioning. The suggestions are grouped into 11 major classes. They were strengthening and empowering chief system, release of more funds for development, special financial assistance for the chief, inclusion of chief in development bodies, construction of village court building, reduction of corruption, employment

generation for the villagers, establishment of village market, empowering youth & women, development of social infrastructure, and development of physical infrastructure (see table 12).

The results indicated that strengthening and empowering of chief system in Manipur is found to be the most prominent suggestion for enhancing the effectiveness of the functioning of the chieftainship by the chiefs themselves. Over three fourth of the chiefs in most developed blocks(78%) and more than one half of them in least developed blocks(58) suggested strengthening and empowering of chief system.

The development of physical infrastructure (58%) and release of more funds for development (53%) were the other two suggestions put forward by the majority of chiefs in the least developed blocks. Special financial assistance for the chief and inclusion of chief in development bodies of the state are the other significant suggestions made by the chiefs. More than one third of the chiefs of least developed blocks(47%) recommended special financial assistance for the chief and inclusion of chief in development bodies of the state while one half of the chiefs recommended the former and another one half of them recommended the latter.

Concluding Observations

Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) do not exist in most of the Tribal Areas of North East India. The PRIs have not been introduced in the Tribal Areas of North East to respect the self-governing traditional institutions of tribal people by the constitution of India. In the Kuki areas of Manipur, there is a “*Semang Pachong*” (Elders Council which gives advice to the chief), which is also similar to the Village Council but the real authority and ultimate discretionary execution power of decisions are vested on the traditional chief. The traditional institution of chieftainship has already been abolished in Mizoram as well as the Naga areas of Manipur and Nagaland states. In these areas, democratically elected chief has already replaced hereditary chiefs periodically though PRIs had yet to be introduced.

In this context, the present study assessed the role of traditional institution of chieftainship in the Kuki areas of Manipur. In infrastructure development, the most developed blocks were better performing as compared to the least developed blocks. In spite of this the social and physical infrastructure development situation in the tribal areas is far from satisfactory. Roads, transport, communication, primary healthcare and education need much more advancement.

The chieftains run the day today administration of the villages of Kuki tribes. They broadly represent the social composition of these tribes in terms of sub tribe and denomination. In economic structural terms, they depend upon agriculture as most of the people of Kuki communities. But in terms of education and income they are slightly better off than the general populace of the villages they administer. The Chiefs belonging to the most developed area were having significantly higher income and greater level of education as expected. The chiefs in both the most developed and least developed blocks perceive the developmental

role very much and report developmental achievements. However, their virtual role in development is far from satisfactory. It could be observed during the field survey that most of the chiefs live in their respective district headquarters or in nearby towns and the people report that their chiefs rarely visit their villages. There is no democratic control over them from below and they are neither responsible for people nor state government. Brief interactions with the village people revealed number problems in the actual working of the institution of chieftainship. The people suffer from nepotism and negligence in the functioning of the chiefs. As the entire village including the land is technically owned by the chiefs, the people are voiceless and powerless. They cannot afford to challenge the chief as he has the power to evict the complainant and seize the house and other properties owned by his or her household. Another serious problem reported by the people was that until recently the chiefs did not allow the people to vote in the general and assembly elections at their will but rather dictated the people to vote to a particular candidate or casted the votes themselves forcefully.

With due regard and respect for Kuki tradition and culture, it could be argued that the institution of the chieftainship in its present form is in a state of decadence and has become obsolete. Today, the institution of the chief functions to fulfill the personal ambitions of the chiefs themselves rather than working towards the collective goals of tribal welfare, development and empowerment.

Therefore, the Sixth Schedule of the Constitution of India should be reviewed at the earliest and the traditional institution of chieftainship should be restricted to ceremonial purposes and to democratize the Kuki society Panchayati Raj institutions with at least a two tier system needs to be introduced. All the efforts should be made to promote awareness among the Kuki people on democratic decentralisation and people's participation in development.

Table 1 Demographic Bases of Chiefs

Sl.No	Characteristic	Type of Blocks		Total N =37
		Least Developed n=19	Most Developed n=18	
I	Gender			
	Male	19 (100.00)	17 (94.44)	36 (97.30)
	Female	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
II	Age Group			
	Young (Below 35)	1 (5.26)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.70)
	Middle (35-60)	11 (57.89)	12 (66.67)	23 (62.16)
	Old (60 and Above)	7 (36.84)	6 (33.33)	13 (35.14)

	Mean Years of Age	57.1 ± 16.4	57.3 ± 12.5	57.2 ± 14.5
III	Marital Status			
	Married	19 (100)	18 (100)	37 (100)
IV	Education Status			
	Illiterate	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Primary (1-4)	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Middle (5-7)	3 (15.79)	0 (0.00)	3 (8.11)
	High School (8-10)	11 (57.89)	14 (77.78)	25 (67.57)
	Higher Secondary and Above	5 (26.32)	2 (11.11)	7 (18.92)
	Mean Years of Education	10.00 ± 3.40	9.17 ± 3.78	9.59 ± 3.56
V	Type of Family			
	Nuclear	3 (15.79)	1 (5.56)	4 (10.81)
	Joint	16 (84.21)	17 (94.44)	33 (89.19)
VI	Size of Family			
	Medium (4-6)	6 (31.58)	3 (16.67)	9 (24.32)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 2 Social Structural Bases of Chiefs

Sl.No	Characteristic	Type of Blocks		Total N =37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
I	Tribe			
	Thado	12 (63.16)	9 (50.00)	21 (56.76)
	Vaiphei	1 (5.26)	6 (33.33)	7 (18.92)
	Gangte	5 (26.32)	2 (11.11)	7 (18.92)
	Zo	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)

	Aimol	1 (5.26)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.70)
II	Religion			
	Christianity	19 (100.00)	16 (88.89)	35 (94.59)
	Judaism	0 (0.00)	2 (11.11)	2 (5.41)
III	Denomination			
	Evangelical	6 (31.58)	7 (38.89)	13 (35.14)
	Baptist	9 (47.37)	2 (11.11)	11 (29.73)
	Presbyterian	1 (5.26)	3 (16.67)	4 (10.81)
	Roman Catholic	1 (5.26)	1 (5.56)	2 (5.41)
	Pentecostal	1 (5.26)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.70)
	Messianic	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Judaism	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Others	1 (5.26)	3 (16.67)	4 (10.81)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 3 Economic Structural Bases of Chiefs

Sl.No	Characteristic	Type of Blocks		Total N =37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
I	Main Occupation			
	Cultivation	16 (84.21)	11 (61.11)	27 (72.97)
	Government Service	3 (15.79)	3 (16.67)	6 (16.22)
	Pension	0 (0.00)	2 (11.11)	2 (5.41)
	Business	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Social Service	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)

II	Subsidiary Occupation			
	None	8 (42.11)	7 (38.89)	15 (40.54)
	Agriculture	5 (26.32)	7 (38.89)	12 (32.43)
	Horticulture	3 (15.79)	1 (5.56)	4 (10.81)
	Business	2 (10.53)	0 (0.00)	2 (5.41)
	Pensioner	0 (0.00)	1 (5.56)	1 (2.70)
	Cottage Industry	0 (0.00)	2 (11.11)	2 (5.41)
	Pharmacy	1 (5.26)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.70)
III	Level of Annual Household Income			
	Below Rs 30000	7 (36.84)	1 (5.56)	8 (21.62)
	Rs 30000 to 60000	8 (42.11)	10 (55.56)	18 (48.65)
	Rs 60000 – 100000	3 (15.79)	3 (16.67)	6 (16.22)
	Above Rs 100000	1 (5.26)	4 (22.22)	5 (13.51)
	Mean Annual Household Income	50421.05 ± 27586.86	76722.22 ± 59541.19	63216.22 ± 47246.48

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages
Mean ± S.D**Table 4 Political Affiliation of Chiefs**

Sl.No	Characteristic	Type of Blocks		Total N =37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
I	Political Affiliation			
	None	9(47.37)	8(44.44)	17(45.95)
	Supporter	10(52.63)	9(50.00)	19(51.35)
	Member	0(0.00)	1(5.56)	1(2.70)
II	Political Party			
	None	9(47.37)	8(44.44)	17(45.95)
	Indian National Congress (INC)	6 (31.58)	6 (33.33)	12 (32.43)
	Rashtriya Janada Dal (RJD)	2 (10.53)	0(0.00)	2(5.41)
	Nationalist Congress Party (NCP)	0(0.00)	2(11.11)	2(5.41)
	Lok Jansakthi Party (LJP)	1(5.26)	1(5.56)	2(5.41)
	Samajwadi Party (SP)	0(0.00)	1(5.56)	1(2.70)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 5 Details of Chieftainship: Duration, Generation, and Modes of Acquisition

Sl.No	Details	Type of Blocks		Total N =37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
I	Duration of Chieftainship			
	Less than 15 Years	5(26.32)	5(27.78)	10(27.03)
	15 – 35 Years	8 (42.11)	7 (38.89)	15 (40.54)
	35 Years and Above	6 (31.58)	6 (33.33)	12 (32.43)
	Mean Years of Acting as Chief	26.74 ± 16.14	28.44 ± 18.60	27.57 ± 17.16
II	Number of Generations as Chief			
	1	6 (31.58)	4 (22.22)	10 (27.03)
	2	6 (31.58)	9 (50.00)	15 (40.54)
	3	3 (15.79)	3 (16.67)	6 (16.22)
	4	1 (5.26)	2 (11.11)	3 (8.11)
	5	3 (15.79)	0 (0.00)	3 (8.11)
	Mean Number of Generations	2.42 ± 1.43	2.17 ± 0.92	2.30 ± 1.20
III	Mode of Acquisition of Chieftainship			
	Elders' Choice	8 (42.11)	6 (33.33)	14 (37.84)
	Purchase	6 (31.58)	6 (33.33)	12 (32.43)
	King/British Appointment	4 (21.05)	4 (22.22)	8 (21.62)
	Others	1 (5.26)	2 (11.11)	3 (8.11)
IV	Generations Expected			
	One Generation	9 (47.37)	9 (50.00)	18 (48.65)
	As Long as Customary Law continued	2 (10.53)	3 (16.67)	5 (13.51)
	So Long as the Lineage Continued	8 (42.11)	6 (33.33)	14 (37.84)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages
Mean ± S.D**Table 6 Pattern of Consultation in Decision Making**

Sl.No	Agency	Type of Blocks				Total N = 37	
		Least Developed n =19		Most Developed n =18		Mean	S.D
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
1	Village Elders	3.42	0.69	3.94	0.24	3.68	0.58
2	Youth Leaders	3.63	0.76	3.56	0.78	3.59	0.76
3	Church Leaders	3.21	1.18	3.67	0.49	3.43	0.93
4	Own Family Members	3.47	0.96	3.39	0.70	3.43	0.83
5	Knowledgeable Persons	3.37	0.83	3.39	0.61	3.38	0.72
6	Relatives	3.05	0.85	3.17	0.92	3.11	0.88
7	Friends	2.47	1.17	3.00	0.97	2.73	1.10
8	School Teachers	2.16	1.26	2.89	1.02	2.51	1.19

Source: Computed

Table 7 Exposures to Official and Non-Official Development Functionaries

Sl.No	Development Functionary	Type of Blocks		Total N = 37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
1	Member of Legislative Assembly (MLA)	17 (89.00)	17 (94.00)	34 (92.00)
2	Block Development Officer (BDO)	17 (89.00)	15 (83.00)	32 (86.00)
3	District Deputy Collector (DDC)	17 (89.00)	15 (83.00)	32 (86.00)
4	Extension Officer (EO)	16 (84.00)	13 (72.00)	29 (78.00)
5	Village Agriculture Worker (VAW)	14 (74.00)	13 (72.00)	27 (73.00)
6	Deputy Commissioner (DC)	12 (63.00)	15 (83.00)	27 (73.00)
7	Primary School Headmaster	14 (74.00)	12 (67.00)	26 (70.00)
8	Village Health Workers (Nurse)	11 (58.00)	12 (67.00)	23 (62.00)
9	Any Police Officer	12 (63.00)	11 (61.00)	23 (62.00)
10	Any Bank Manager	9 (47.00)	8 (44.00)	17 (46.00)
11	State Ministers	8 (42.00)	6 (33.00)	14 (38.00)
12	Member of Parliament (MP)	6 (32.00)	0 (0.00)	6 (16.00)
	Exposure to Development Functionaries Index	0.67 ± 0.19	0.63 ± 0.23	0.65 ± 0.21

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages
Mean ± S.D**Table 8 Role Perception of Chiefs**

Sl.No	Function	Type of Blocks				Total N = 37	
		Least Developed n =19		Most Developed n =18		Mean	S.D
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
1	Monitoring Forest Clearance	2.00	1.15	2.00	1.14	2.00	1.13
2	Deciding Date of Forest Clearance	3.21	0.85	2.44	1.04	2.84	1.01
3	Distribution of Land	3.21	0.79	2.83	0.92	3.03	0.87
4	Deciding Land Site for Cultivation	3.53	0.77	3.06	1.00	3.30	0.91
5	Protecting the Village	3.53	0.51	3.56	0.51	3.54	0.51
6	Ensuring Order and Justice	3.68	0.58	3.56	0.51	3.62	0.55
7	Promoting Hard Work etc	3.79	0.54	3.72	0.46	3.76	0.49
8	Promoting Integration	3.89	0.46	3.67	0.49	3.78	0.48
9	Promoting Religiosity & Spirituality	3.84	0.50	3.78	0.43	3.81	0.46
10	Promoting Honesty	4.00	0.00	3.67	0.49	3.84	0.37
11	Improving Living Condition	3.79	0.71	3.61	0.50	3.70	0.62
12	Promoting Self Help	3.79	0.54	3.67	0.49	3.73	0.51
13	Preventing spread of disease	3.84	0.50	3.72	0.46	3.78	0.48
14	Promoting Education	3.95	0.23	3.89	0.32	3.92	0.28
I	Traditional Role (1:10)	3.47	0.62	3.23	0.70	3.35	0.68
II	Developmental Role (11:14)	3.84	0.49	3.72	0.44	3.78	0.47

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 9 Perceived Achievements of the Chiefs: Traditional and Developmental

Sl.No	Achievement	Type of Blocks		Total N = 37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
1	Physical Infrastructure	14 (73.68)	15 (83.33)	29 (78.38)
2	Social Infrastructure	13 (68.42)	14 (77.78)	27 (72.97)
3	Settlement of Disputes and Justice	11 (57.89)	10 (55.56)	21 (56.76)
4	Economic Development	12 (63.16)	8 (44.44)	20 (54.05)
5	Implementation of Customary Law	1 (5.26)	2 (11.11)	3 (8.11)
6	Administrative Development	3 (15.79)	5 (27.78)	8 (21.62)
I	Traditional Achievement Index (3+5+6)	0.26 ± 0.18	0.31 ± 0.24	0.29 ± 0.21
II	Developmental Achievement Index (1+3+4)	0.68 ± 0.28	0.69 ± 0.33	0.68 ± 0.30

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages
Mean ± S.D**Table 10 Correlates of Role Perception and Achievements of Chief**

Variable	Exposure to Development Functionaries	Role Perception		Achievement	
		Traditional Role	Developmental Role	Traditional	Developmental
Type of Blocks	-0.09	-0.30	-0.14	0.12	0.00
Age Group	-0.23	-0.14	-0.11	0.38*	-0.09
Education Status	0.05	0.16	0.14	0.10	-0.07
Level of Income	-0.03	-0.23	-0.15	0.28	-0.05
Duration of Chieftainship	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.24	-0.04
Number of Generation as Chief	0.06	0.12	-0.05	-0.02	0.04
Exposure to Development Functionaries	1	0.23	0.03	0.13	0.31
Traditional Role Perception	0.23	1.00	0.66 **	-0.05	0.15
Developmental Role Perception	0.03	0.66 **	1.00	-0.21	-0.09
Traditional Achievement	0.13	-0.05	-0.21	1.00	0.11
Developmental Achievement	0.31	0.15	-0.09	0.11	1

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages
* P< 0.05 **P<0.01**Table 11 Constraints to Effective Functioning of Chiefs**

Sl.No	Constraint	Type of Blocks		Total N = 37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
1	Dealing with Insurgent Groups	10 (52.63)	10 (55.56)	20 (54.05)
2	Poverty and Illiteracy	10 (52.63)	8 (44.44)	18 (48.65)
3	Lack of Unity Among Villagers	9 (47.37)	7 (38.89)	16 (43.24)
3	Lack of Infrastructure Development	6 (31.58)	5 (27.78)	11 (29.73)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Note: Multiple responses were obtained

Table 12 Suggestions for Effective Functioning of Chief System

Sl.No		Type of Blocks		Total N = 37
		Least Developed n =19	Most Developed n =18	
1	Strengthening and Empowering Chief System	11 (57.89)	14 (77.78)	25 (67.57)
2	Release More Funds for Development	10 (52.63)	12 (66.67)	22 (59.46)
3	Special Financial Assistance for the Chief	9 (47.37)	11 (61.11)	20 (54.05)
4	Inclusion of chief in Development Body	9 (47.37)	9 (50.00)	18 (48.65)
5	Construction of Village Court Building	4 (21.05)	4 (22.22)	8 (21.62)
6	Reduction of Corruption	4 (21.05)	3 (16.67)	7 (18.92)
7	Employment Generation for the Villagers	6 (31.58)	5 (27.78)	11 (29.73)
8	Establishment of Village Market	5 (26.32)	2 (11.11)	7 (18.92)
9	Empowering Youth & Women	5 (26.32)	3 (16.67)	8 (21.62)
10	Development of Social Infrastructure	9 (47.37)	5 (27.78)	14 (37.84)
11	Development of Physical Infrastructure	11 (57.89)	5 (27.78)	16 (43.24)

Source: Computed

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Note: Multiple responses were obtained

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